

Formulaic language in a multilingual community of practice: Latin and the vernacular in legal discourse

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1. Introduction

For this presentation I've been inspired to look at formulaic language from two perspectives which have recently come to the fore in English historical linguistics: multilingualism and communities of practice (CoP). These contexts are not new or original for research into present-day language variation and change. Links between formulaic language and multilingual repertoires in current language use have been made by various scholars (especially in L2 acquisition, for a recent overview see Van Vu and Peters 2023; see also special edition of *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics* 2012 vol.32) and CoP framework has been used to explain some instances of formulaic language (Kopaczyk 2013a, 2013b).

These two perspectives present several challenges when dealing with historical data, which is what I will concentrate on in this contribution to the workshop. My source of examples and case studies will be the linguistic situation in medieval and early modern Scotland, and in particular the development of vernacular legal discourse. The first two sections below will lay out the theoretical premise and existing research in historical multilingualism and CoPs, then I'll introduce the linguistic situation and the development of legal discourse in Scotland. In the final part of the presentation, I'll discuss a case study of formulaic language arising in a multilingual CoP context, identifying challenges, remaining questions and suggesting ways forward.

What we need to know:

- What was formulaic in administrative Latin?
- How these formulaic patterns made their way into vernacular writing?
- To what extent vernacular formulaicity depends on Latin formulaicity?

2. Medieval Latin and multilingualism

The medieval period is an obvious context for the study of multilingual repertoires because of the overwhelming presence of Latin in administrative and business records (see Bedos-Rezak 1996), religious texts, as well as other genres. Underneath the layer of Latin text culture visible to us today, there was spoken communication in vernacular languages, which slowly developed the tools and required prestige to take over from Latin in the written realm (a process which was not completed in some parts of Europe until the 18c). Still, until relatively recently, histories of vernacular European languages did not take into account the structural synchronic impact of Latin on scribal vernacular practice, the focus being on lexical borrowing over time. Among recent trends in historical linguistics are those engaging with multilingual repertoires and the resulting range of multilingual practices (Pahta et al. 2018), from code-switching, through language mixing to (trans)languaging. “Such practices can be discerned in historical material where the construction and reception of intended meaning relies on engaging with more than one linguistic resource” (Kopaczyk 2022: 121). It must be added that Latin was not reserved for writing and that some people used Latin in spoken communication, even outside the religious context (Sharpe 1996, Putter 2016, Putter et al. 2023: 409).

In the context of formulaic language, the interaction between Latin and the vernacular language, both forming the linguistic repertoire of a scribe, could thus be threefold:

1. The vernacular borrows set phrases from written (or spoken) Latin without translation. An early form of this process would be code-switching, or the change of linguistic resource on the level of phrase or clause. The Latin formula is then retained in its original form in the vernacular, like *hic incipit* or *per annum*. It is reasonable to assume that a formulaic phrase of this kind would already have become formulaic in Latin, and that it would remain formulaic (i.e. prone to structural adaptations and retrieved wholesale) over time.
2. The vernacular translates a Latin set phrase (or a non-phrasal formulaic chunk) with the necessary adjustments to grammar and lexicon; in other words, it produces a

structural calque. For example *Sciendum est* becomes *It is to wyt* in Middle Scots administrative records (see the discussion below and the Appendix).

3. A formulaic chunk from the vernacular, most often a phrase, becomes embedded in the Latin written discourse, to capture the specificity of the local culture (legal, religious, mercantile, etc.), e.g. *in defensionibus defendando wrang and unlawe* (from Scottish burgh laws).

A potentially fruitful research avenue would be to find instances of these three scenarios and compare them across different vernacular contexts. It would also be useful to think about other outcomes of Latin+vernacular multilingualism in the context of formulaicity. Working with Middle English administrative records, Stenroos and Schipor (2020) looked at shift in the linguistic resource in “multilingual events”, where Predictability of the shift could be formulaic, when a “set phrase” from another language was employed in a text, or customary, when the genre dictated language choices e.g. a goods inventory written in mixed language (see Wright 2015).

3. Communities of practice

In terms of helping to understand how formulaic language is shaped and transmitted through text and time, communities of practice (CoP) seem to be the best explanatory sociolinguistic framework. The concept of a CoP originated in the theory of social learning and interactions between members of a workplace (Lave and Wenger 1991). Wenger (1998: 72-85) talks about three dimensions of CoPs: joint enterprise, mutual engagement, and shared tools or a shared repertoire. In the introduction to our edited collection which for the first time applied the CoP framework to historical linguistic inquiries (Kopaczyk and Jucker (eds.) 2013), we showed how these dimensions translate to historical contexts. The two central concepts are reification and participation. The first is about producing some kind of form which “becomes a focus for the negotiation of meaning” (Wenger 1998: 59). That form is generated because of participation, and participation is enabled through interaction with the created form. So a reified form is something encoded and then decoded by the community, for example an instance or a type of formulaic language use. Recently, we've tightened the understanding of the framework along the following lines:

(a) Joint enterprise: This is the reason why a community comes together to engage in a particular activity, for example the production of administrative documents. We can extrapolate from the reifications of community practice to establish the nature of the joint enterprise. Historical contexts also open a diachronic dimension where “[s]ome linguistic and textual practices were passed on, some were altered, however the joint enterprise continued. In a way, it is an example of a ‘joined-up’ diachronic enterprise, which remained relatively stable while the shared repertoire [...] was reviewed and negotiated by the members joining the community as the time moved on.” (Kopaczyk and Jucker forthcoming)

(b) Mutual engagement: Present-day sociolinguistic studies emphasise that “[a] CoP requires regular and mutually defining interaction” (Holmes and Meyerhoff 1999: 179). For historical contexts, there are two plains on which that could happen. “The interaction and engagement may [...] happen directly between the current members, or they may happen indirectly through texts which are the products of the community’s joint enterprise. That type of diachronic interaction is still “regular” and “mutually defining” – for example, scribes would regularly consult previous texts during their training.” (Kopaczyk and Jucker forthcoming).

(a) Shared repertoire: Formulaic language use is one possible outcome of a joint enterprise and mutual engagement, realised by a CoP. It can be part of a broader shared repertoire, including “both verbal and non-verbal elements (routines, tools, artifacts)”, as pointed out by Timofeeva in her research on monastic life (2013: 203-204; 2022: 24). My previous research has drawn on the CoP framework to illuminate the emergence of high degrees of textual standardisation (Kopaczyk 2013a, 2013b), including phrasal and non-phrasal highly frequent chunks of text (up to 8-grams) in medieval administrative and legal records from Scotland.

4. Vernacularisation of legal discourse in Scotland

Just like in other countries across Europe, in medieval Scotland Latin was used as a default language in local legal and administrative record. From the late 14th century onwards, we witness the beginning of the vernacularisation process, whereby the

spoken language of administrative and trading centres - the burghs in the Scottish Lowlands - started to be used in official record alongside Latin (see e.g. Havinga 2021). We know this language today as Scots, and it can be conceived of as a sister language to English down south, emerging from the northernmost Old English (Anglian) dialects with an admixture of Scandinavian influences from the Danelaw area of northern England. That language was on its own path towards standardisation, much like other vernaculars of the day, including English. It is through extralinguistic pressures of the centre of prestige and power in the south, especially after the introduction of the printing press and the Reformation, combined with political developments such as the Unions of the Crowns (1603) and Parliaments (1707), that Scots was largely removed from high registers in Scotland in which it had flourished in medieval and early modern times. It has survived in the spoken domain and its relationship to Scottish Standard English is best conceptualised as a register continuum (for a recent introduction to the history of Scots see Millar 2023).

Havinga's study of vernacularisation in the Aberdeen Council Registers (2021) has demonstrated that the entries in Scots start around 1430s and rise up to 30% of all entries over the course of four decades. After 1480 the rise in Scots is sharper and stabilises at about 70% of all entries by the early 16th century. What this means is that despite the introduction of the vernacular into record-keeping, Latin is still very much part of an active multilingual repertoire of the generations of scribes compiling the registers. The study has also looked at switches from Scots to Latin within selected records (1441-1472), following Schendl's suggestion (2002: 70) that increased vernacularisation prompts increased code-switching. That trend was, indeed, corroborated, and it strengthens the argument about the existence of a multilingual complex code in the minds and practices of the scribes, where the languages exert mutual influence on all levels of linguistic complexity, from discourse chunks to spelling conventions (see Kopaczyk 2021). For our purposes here, what is important to know is that switches to Latin are most frequently intersentential (i.e. between independent clauses, Schendl 2011: 69) or phrasal. That is because the practice of, for example, giving the date and other header information would continue in Latin even though the body of the entry was written in Scots, see Example (1) from the annotated version of the Aberdeen corpus (Havinga 2021).

(1)

```
<div type="entry" xml:id="ARO-5-0782-01" xml:lang="sco">
```

```
<p> <lb break="yes"/> <foreign xml:lang="lat">Vndecimo die me's' Noue'br' Anno q' sup'</foreign> / It  
was ordanit be the Aldirman and
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<lb break="yes"/> Counsaile for the com'oune p'ffit of this burgh' / that al the p'sounes bath' men
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<lb break="yes"/> and wemen / the quhilk' ar sclaud'it of spillyng of the m'kate / sal forber'
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What is interesting to note is that the Latin and the vernacular form a visually continuous sequence (see the line breaks in the tagged text in (1)), which further enhances the argument about a single multilingual code in operation here.

5. Formulaic chunks across languages in medieval and early modern legal genres

5.1. How to track formulaicity?

In my work I've been concentrating on automatic retrieval of stable repetitive chunks of text, i.e. lexical bundles (Kopaczyk 2013a), which requires a corpus with normalised spelling. This is often the first hurdle for historical texts where a large degree of spelling variation is the norm. Artificial spelling normalisation can be achieved with tools such as VARD (Baron and Rayson 2008), however doing it for under-researched and under-resourced languages can be problematic, as normalisation tools typically operate with standard vocabularies designed on the basis of present-day major standard languages. There are promising trends in NLP and AI-driven approaches to spelling normalisation (Robertson 2017, Bawden et al. 2022), which will hopefully extend to formulaic sequence retrieval.

5.2. How much is formulaic language in medieval and early modern legal genres influenced by Latin?

In an exploratory study (Kopaczyk 2020), I looked at one of the earliest coherent body of laws from Scotland, the so called *Leges Burgorum* or *Lawis of Burrowis*, which were compiled both in Latin and in Scots throughout the medieval and early modern period. The idea was that the text of a particular legal provision was intended to contain the same set of instructions or regulations, so I wanted to check how formulaic the Latin

versions were, and how much of that formulaic repertoire was then taken up by scribes writing in Scots.

I selected four laws, carried out lemmatisation to get rid of spelling variants and grammatical variants, and collated the text of the same laws from a range of Latin manuscripts (Fig. 1) and then from Scots manuscripts, using an automatic collation tool Juxta Commons (Wheels and Jensen 2013). The darker the blue, the more differences at a given point in the text between the witnesses. Conversely, the white bits and light blue bits are the most stable elements in the text of a given law; they recur across the witnesses in exactly the same or roughly the same wording. These sequences therefore make good candidates for the status of a formulaic sequence on the basis of their structural stability.

Fig. 1. Juxta Commons collation of 7 Latin manuscript witnesses of a selection of laws from *Leges Burgorum*.

There are 37 stable chunks across the Latin versions. I identified corresponding chunks in the Scots versions, presented in Appendix. Several observations can be made on the basis of this collation:

(1) There is much more formulaic discourse in the Latin text of the same set of laws than there is in their vernacular versions, as revealed by a range of equivalents for the majority of Latin stable chunks. This might be due to the fact that the Latin tradition was developed earlier and had a chance to crystallise over the decades and centuries of scribal practice.

(2) Conversely, the vernacular versions show a large degree of variation in lexical choices and grammatical structures, and even in the presence or absence of some bits of text, which raises questions about copying practices within the vernacular tradition. It looks like the versions may have been translated from Latin each time rather than copied from an earlier Scots exemplar.

(3) The discrepancies between the vernacular versions also highlight the early stages of developing legal discourse. Still, there is some agreement between groups of manuscripts (for details, see Kopaczyk 2020). This might be due to a common exemplar or to a shared linguistic practice, also across time, as the manuscripts are not all coeval.

(4) In terms of formulaicity, it is interesting to see that the most stable chunks across the vernacular versions are not necessarily phrasal.

Following from that, a comparison between the stable Latin chunks and their Scots counterparts (see Appendix) reveals the following scenarios:

- (a) textual standardisation in Scots due to Latin influence,
- (b) Scots lexical choices influenced by Latin,
- (c) Scots structural choices influenced by Latin,
- (d) textual standardisation regardless of Latin.

I present a detailed discussion of these in Kopaczyk (2020). In summary, only 5 stable Latin chunks prompted stable vernacular rendition across all manuscripts but also a few phraseological choices, for example binomial constructions, were modelled on the Latin example: cf. *vivus et mortuus* > *quyck and dede* 'alive and dead'. Direct relationship between stable vernacular chunks and Latin was demonstrated in 18 out of 37 contexts, while in the remainder there was either no clear winner in the vernacular versions, or the winning option was not inspired by Latin.

The study summarised here may be used as a starting point for a much more comprehensive investigation of recurrent stable fragments of Latin vs vernacular discourse. Ideally, all extant manuscripts of the laws should be digitised into a machine-readable format, and then collated and compared. Unfortunately Juxta

Commons, which was an excellent and intuitive piece of software, is no longer supported. I would welcome suggestions what other tools can be used for the same purpose.

6. Further research directions.

There are multiple threads of further research which stem from the above presentation. Firstly, there are various definitions of formulaic language and there is space for a fruitful discussion of which of those are most useful for historical inquiries. Secondly, in terms of situating formulaic language use in a social and cultural context, more work can be done on the application of various sociolinguistic frameworks, including CoPs, to conceptualise its creation and transmission. There is also scope to extend this type of research beyond administrative and legal records, which have admittedly dominated the field of formulaic language from a historical perspective. For example, elements in letters have been described as formulaic or ritualistic (e.g. Conde-Silvestre 2021) and there is much scope to look for formulaicity and its forms and functions in early scientific and medical discourse as well (cf. Kopaczyk 2013c). Another direction is to look for interactions between Latin and vernacular languages across different linguistic contexts. It would be interesting to see whether the same bits of Latin were perceived as worthy of rendering wholesale in the local language, and if yes, whether equivalent calqued versions were adopted. A good example would be *Anno Domini*, a prevalent formulaic Latin chunk which gets replaced by both *the year of God* and *the year of our Lord* in English and Scots. Is it because *Anno Dei* was also used in similar context, and if yes, what about the equivalents in other European languages?

A final plea would be to develop collaborations with computer scientists to create robust and easy to use collation tools, which enable comparisons between multiple versions of the same text.

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APPENDIX

Chapter 17

(1) *sciendum quod*

- *It is to wyt* (ScA, ScG), *It is to vyt* (ScB)
- *And it is to wyt* (ScC), *And it is to wytte* (ScE), *And It is to wit* (ScD, ScF)

(2) *non debet*

- *acht no^t to be* (ScA), *aw noȝt to be* (ScB), *aucht nocht to be* (ScG)
- *sall nocht be* (ScC, ScE), *sall no^t be* (ScD, ScF)

Chapter 23

(3) *de* [+noun] *burgensis*

- *Off burgeß* [+noun] (ScB, ScF), *Off burges* [+noun] (ScD, ScE)
- *Off borow ma(n)nys* [+noun] (ScC)
- *Of* [+noun] *on a burges* (ScG)

(4) *si burgensis terram vel terras* [+verb]

- *Geyff aburgeß haß gottin land or land(is)* (ScB)
- *Gyfe a burges has gotyn ony land* (ScG)
- *Gyff ye burges gettys ony lande* (ScC), *Gyff a burgeß gettis ony land* (ScD), *Giff a burgeß gettis ony land* (ScF)
- *Gyf a burges gett(is) ony land(is)* (ScE)

(5) *in burgo*

- *in burgh* (ScB), *in the burgh* (ScG)
- *wⁱin burgh* (ScD), *wⁱin bur^t* (ScF), *wythin burche* (ScE)
- *within ye king(is) burgh* (ScC)

(6) *et puerum heredem habuerit*

- *and he haue a chylde till h(is) ayre* (ScB), *and he haue a chylde till his aire* (ScD), *and he hafe a chylde tyl his ayre* (ScG)
- *and he haue a childe tyll ayre* (ScE)
- *ande he have ony chylde to ayre* (ScC)
- *and he hafe achild till aw* (ScF)

(7) *et eas non assignaverit*

- *and ye lande be vn assignit* (ScB)
- *and has no^t assignit his land to nane* (ScF, ScD)
- *Ande hafe nocht assignyt his land(is) to na man* (ScC), *& haff nocht assegnit his landys to na ma(n)* (ScE)
- *and he assigne to nane* (ScG)

(8) *ante mortem suam*

- *befor h(is) destiß* (ScB)
- *before his dede* (ScG)
- *eftyr(e) his dede* (ScD)
- *eftyr his deceß* (ScD), *Eft(ir) his dysses* (ScE), *eftir his deceß* (ScF)

(9) *filius ... vel filia ... heres*

- *his son(n)e or doȝt(ir)* (ScB), *his sone or dochtyr* (ScD), *his soin~ or docht(ir)* (ScE), *his son~ or docht(ir)* (ScF)
- *his son~ or his docht(ir) ayr(is)* (ScD), *his ayre sone or dochtyr* (ScG)

(10) *hereditatem ... terre ... quam ... die ...*

- *all ye herytage ... ye quhilk ... yat day* (ScB), *ye h(er)etage ... y^t day* (ScF)
- *ye heritage of all ye land(is) ... ye day* (ScC)

- *ye heretage of all of his fadir had y^t day* (ScD), *ye herytage of all his fadre hayde yat day* (ScE)

- *ye eritage of all ye land ... qwhil* (ScG)

(11) *fuit vivus et mortuus*

- *he vas leyffand and ded* (ScB)

- *he was quyk and dede* (ScC), *he wes quik and dede* (ScD), *he was qwheke and dede* (ScE), *he was quike and dede* (ScF)

- *he was in lyfe and qwhen he deid* (ScG)

(12) *salvo ... quod uxor*

- *outtakand yat h(is) spoussit vyff* (ScB), *Outane yat his spousyt wyfe* (ScG)

- *sauff y^t his wyfe* (ScC), *sauff y^t his wyff* (ScD), *safe yat his wyfe* (ScE), *sauf y^t his wife* (ScF)

(13) *tota vita sua quamdiu erit vidua*

- *all h(ir) lyff alβ lang as scho Is vedow* (ScB), *al hyr lyfe als lang as scho is wydow* (ScG)

- *in all hir(e) lyfe* (ScC), *in all hyr liff* (ScD), *in all hire lyfe* (ScE), *In all hir life* (ScF)

(14) *interiorem partem domus*

- *ye Inn(er)mast part of ye howβ* (ScB), *ye ennyr p(ar)t of ye house* (ScG)

- *ye e(n)n(ir)halfe of ye houβ* (ScC), *the Inn(ir)half of the houβ* (ScD), *the Innirhafe of the hous* (ScE), *ye Inn(ir) half of ye houβ* (ScF)

(15) *que dicitur ...*

- *ye quhilk is callyt* (ScB)

- *yat is callyt* (ScC)

(16) *tenebit*

- *sall haue* (ScB, ScD, ScE), *sall hafe* (ScC)

- *sall Joiβ* (ScF)

(17) *heres ... ulteriorem partem domus*

- *ye ayr ye Inn(ir) mast p(ar)t of ye p(ri)ncypall houβ* (ScB)
- *ye ayre sall hafe ye toy(ir) halfe of ye hevyd houβ* (ScC)
- *ye air ye heid houβ* (ScF)

(18) *si in ea habitare voluerit*

- *geyff yat he vill duell in it* (ScB), *gyf he wyll dwell in it* (ScG)
- *gif hym lik(is) to wyn or duell yar(e) in* (ScC)

(19) *et hoc dico si uxor*

- *and yat I say geyff yat vyff* (ScB)
- *Ande yis I say gif ye wyfe* (ScC), *And yis I say gif the wyff* (ScD), *Ande y's I say gyf ye wyfe* (ScE), *And yis I say gif ye wife* (ScF), *And yis I say gyfe the wyfe* (ScG)

(20) *dotem*

- *dowary* (ScB), *dowery* (ScG)
- *morwyngyft* (ScC), *mornyn gift* (ScD), *morowingeft* (ScE), *morowing gift* (ScF)

(21) *si aliam dotem habuerit ipsa ...*

- *and geyff forsuth scho haue oy(ir) dowary* (ScB)
- *And gyfe scho has uthyr dowery* (ScG)
- *and gif scho has oyir(e) morwyngyft* (ScC)
- *bot and scho haue othis* (ScD)

(22) *et ... gaudebit*

- *scho sall Joyβ* (ScB), *scho sall Joiβ* (ScF), *scho sall joys* (ScG)
- *scho sall Joys it J aw* (ScC)

Chapter 27

(23) *novus burgensis*

- *new burges* (ScA, ScC), *nav burgeβ* (ScB), *new burgeβ* (ScF)
- *burgeβ new* (ScD), *burges new* (ScE)
- *burges* (ScG)

(24) *de terra vasta*

- *of waist lande (ScA), off waste lande (ScC), of waist Land (ScD), of wast lande (ScE), of waste land (ScF)*
- *of a vast land (ScB), of a wast land (ScG)*

(25) *et nullam terram habuerit hospitatum*

- *and he haue na land (ScD, ScF), and he haff na lande (ScE)*
- *& has na land biggit (ScA), & he haf na land byggyt (ScG)*
- *and he haue na land for-to duell in till (ScB)*
- *and he have na lande within ye burgh herberyt (ScC)*

(26) *et post ... annum*

- *& eft(ir) y^t ȝer (ScA), and eft(ir) yat ȝher(e) (ScB), and aftyr yat yhere (ScG)*
- *And eft(ir) ye fyrst yher(e) (ScC)*
- *bot eftyr the first zere (ScD), bot eftir ye first zere (ScF)*

(27) *si postea*

- *& gif eft(ir) yat (ScA)*
- *and geyff eft(ir) uart(is) (ScB)*
- *Ande giff (ScC), And gif (ScF)*
- *And gif ... syn(e) (ScD), gyf ... syne (ScE)*
- *And eftir yat gyf (ScG)*

(28) *per ignem vel per guerram et aliam*

- *thru fyr or were (ScA), thrw fyre ot thrw were (ScC), throw fire or were (ScE)*
- *be fyr(e) or ver(e) (ScB), be fyre or were (ScD), be fire or were (ScF)*
- *be wast thrw fyre or were (ScG)*

(29) *hospitatum ... inhospitatum*

- *biggit ... wnbiggit (ScA), byggyt ... vnbyggyt (ScB), byggyd ... vnbyggit (ScC), biggit ... vnbyggit (ScD), bigit ... wnbyggit (ScE), biggit ... vn byggit (ScF), , byggyt ... unbyggyt (ScG),*

(30) *donec fuerit*

- *quhil ye tym he be* (ScA)
- *quhill he be* (ScC), *qwhell he be* (ScE), *q(uh)ll he be* (ScF), *qwhyl he be* (ScG)
- *alß lang as he haß* (ScB)

(31) *salva tamen*

- *bot neu(ir) ye leß* (ScB), *Bot neu(ir) ye less* (ScE), *bot neu(ir)yeles* (ScF)
- *Neveryeles saufe* (ScG)
- *Bot non(e)theleß our all* (ScD)
- *saufande our(e) all* (ScC)

Chapter 33

(32) *impedimenta*

- *impedime(n)t(is)* (ScA), *impedyme(n)tt(is)* (ScB), *impedymntis* (ScG)
- *poyntis* (ScD), *poynttis* (ScE, ScF)
- *thyng(is)* (ScC)

(33) *si dominus eius*

- *gif his lorde* (ScA), *geyff h(is) lord* (ScB), *giff his lorde* (ScC), *gif his lord* (ScD), *gyfe his lorde* (ScE), *gyf his lord* (ScF)
- *gyfe yar lorde* (ScG)

(34) *in exercitu regis*

- *in y^t king(is) hoost* (ScA), *in the kingis oist* (ScD), *in the king(is) ost* (ScE), *in ye kingis oist* (ScF), *in ye kyngys oste* (ScG)
- *in ye king(is) batall or in his ost* (ScB)
- *in ye kyng(is) offys or(e) oste* (ScC)

(35) *vel fuerit in*

- *And ane oy(ir) is gif his lord war in* (ScA)
- *or eft(ir)yat he be in* (ScB)
- *or in* (ScC, ScD, ScE, ScF)
- *or gyfe he be in* (ScG)

(36) *si*

- *gif* (ScA, ScD, ScF), *geyff* (ScB), *giff* (ScC), *gef* (ScE), *gyfe* (ScG)

(37) *pro cibo domini sui*

- *to by his lord(is) met* (ScA)

- *fo ye bying of ye lord(is) mette vyth quham he duellis* (ScB)

- *for bying(e) of his mastr(is) mete w^t quham he dwellis* (ScD), *for bying(e) bying(e)*

[sic] off his mast(ir)ys mete wytht qwhame he dwellys (ScE), *for bying of his maist(er)is*

mete w^t quham he duellis (ScF)

- *for bying off maist(ir) meit yat is his lorde with quham he Duellis.* (ScC)

- *for his masters mete* (ScG)